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Next generation sequencing for non-typhoidal *Salmonella*: Characterization and identification of virulence and antimicrobial resistance for food safety surveillance - An overview

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Abstract- Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technologies have revolutionized bacterium DNA analysis, providing a rapid and cost-effective tool for surveillance. NGS allows a variety of analyses, including multilocus sequence typing, identification of antibiotic resistance, and pathogenicity characterization. Non-Typhoidal *Salmonella* (NTS), a zoonotic pathogen, represents a significant threat to food safety since it is considered as a common contaminant of food animals. Genomic factors that encode bacterial virulence and antimicrobial resistance are crucial for understanding NTS pathogenesis. Next-generation sequencing enables molecular detection, serological assays, and genotyping, providing insights into virulence and antibiotic resistance factors. NGS coupled with bioinformatics tools, emerges as a potent molecular technology, transforming microbiology through genetic sequencing technologies. The landscape of molecular research in food safety is rapidly transitioning from traditional molecular subtyping methods to typing methods based on Next Generation Sequencing (NGS). In this review, we explore the use of next generation sequencing in the analysis of Non-Typhoidal *Salmonella* DNA, particularly its effectiveness in typing bacterial strains and identifying genes linked to virulence and antibiotic resistance. This highlights the significant contributions of NGS to microbiological research in food safety.

Key words: Antimicrobial Resistance gene, Multilocus Sequence Typing (MLST), Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS), Non-Typhoidal *Salmonella* (NTS), Serotyping, Virulence, Whole-Generation Sequencing (WGS)

INTRODUCTION

Non-typhoidal *Salmonella* (NTS) is a leading cause of food-borne diseases worldwide as it stands as one of the leading contributors to diarrheal illnesses, representing a major public health challenge. The genus *Salmonella* is prevalent among food animals, making it a common cause of foodborne diseases worldwide. Human infections caused

by NTS primarily occur through the consumption of contaminated food or water.¹⁻³ Infections caused by the pathogenic bacterial species *Salmonella enterica* impose significant global health burdens. This widely distributed species comprises approximately 2600 distinct serovars categorized as either typhoidal or non-typhoidal *Salmonella*. Despite their genetic similarities, these two groups induce entirely different illnesses and elicit distinct immune responses in human beings.^{4,5} Non-typhoidal

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Salmonella infections are considered zoonotic, as they can be transmitted between animals and humans. Salmonellosis encompasses a spectrum of illnesses affecting both humans and animals, ranging from acute gastroenteritis to bacteraemia and extra-intestinal infections. While NTS intestinal infections are typically self-limiting, prompt antimicrobial therapy is crucial when the bacteria disseminate outside the intestine.^{6,7}

Salmonellosis is more prevalent in developing nations, with multidrug-resistant *Salmonella* posing a significant threat, particularly in South America, Africa, and Asia.⁸ The inadequate control programs and the lack of information from developing countries contribute to the underreporting of *Salmonella* in global surveillance systems.⁹ These countries, even though they are participating in the One Health program which addresses health issues in humans, animal, and environment, face challenges in its implementation. In these countries, particular attention is given to zoonotic pathogens like Non-typhoidal *Salmonella*. The latter illustrates the kind of zoonotic risk One Health strategies seek to address, especially where food safety and transmission of diseases from animals to humans are major public health concerns.^{10,11}

The complexity of NTS is compounded by numerous genes encoding virulence and antibiotic resistance factors critical to the bacteria's pathogenesis.¹² *Salmonella* strains harbour numerous virulence factors distributed throughout the genome, including the *Salmonella* pathogenicity islands (SPIs) and mobile genetic elements like plasmids and prophages. Some components are shared across all *Salmonella* serotypes, while others are serovar-specific.¹ While the presence of various virulence factors within NTS underlines the complexity of their pathogenic mechanisms, the situation is further complicated by the emergence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR). The latter encompasses numerous genes encoding resistance to antimicrobial agents. These genes are often located on plasmids, transposons, gene cassettes, or variants of *Salmonella* Genomic Islands.⁷

To address *Salmonella*'s virulence and resistance challenges, Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) proves effective as an emerging technology allowing for the comprehensive analysis of an organism's genome. It proves to be a quick and efficient method in foodborne disease surveillance.¹³ Compared to conventional testing methods, NGS provides more detailed information on the genotypic

traits of a pathogen, including its virulence factors and antibiotic resistance determinants. This assists in understanding and controlling its pathogenic traits. Recent research indicates that NGS accurately predicts pathogenicity and antimicrobial properties of various pathogens, including *Salmonella*, providing valuable insights into the pathogenic potential of the bacteria.^{1,14,15} Microbiology is thus undergoing a transformative revolution with advances in genome sequencing technologies. When combined with bioinformatics tools, next generation sequencing becomes a powerful technology with a wide range of applications.¹⁶

In this paper, we present a broad overview of Non-typhoidal *Salmonella*, addressing its taxonomy, nomenclature, pathogenicity and the critical issue of multidrug resistance. Additionally, we examine the role of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) in revolutionizing NTS surveillance since these technologies enable a detailed analysis of pathogens' genomic traits, marking a transformative era in the field of food safety surveillance.

Non-typhoidal *Salmonella*: An overview

Global Impact of Non-typhoidal *Salmonella*

Salmonellosis is among the most prevalent infections worldwide. The global health burden caused by NTS is significant because these infections are being predominantly transmitted through the consumption of contaminated food or water.¹⁷ In fact, 94% of *Salmonella* cases are linked to foodborne transmission, with common sources including raw vegetables, unpasteurized dairy products, undercooked eggs, poultry, beef, and pig.¹⁸ NTS accounts for approximately 93.8 million cases of gastroenteritis annually worldwide, with an estimated 80.3 million cases attributed to foodborne transmission alone, and about 155,000 human deaths each year.^{19,20} Salmonellosis encompasses a spectrum of illnesses ranging from self-limiting gastroenteritis to more serious, potentially fatal, extra-intestinal infections like bacteraemia. In fact, non-developing countries, particularly in Asia and Africa, are the most harmed with such pathogens.²¹⁻²⁸ In Africa, NTS infections, being one of the major causes of bacteraemia, appear to be endemic, mostly in children.^{24,29} These illnesses most occur in sub-Saharan Africa. A recent meta-analysis showed that there were an estimated 535 000 non-typhoidal *Salmonella* invasive disease illnesses and that 77 500 deaths were due to this disease in 2017.^{21,24-27,30} In Asia, similar death rates were observed for invasive NTS infections.^{22,23} Overall, several Non-typhoidal *Salmonella*

serovars capable of causing invasive diseases are showing resistance to multiple antimicrobial agents, including those recommended for clinical treatments. The development of antimicrobial resistance in NTS serovars has far-reaching implications. Beyond compromising the effectiveness of standard treatment protocols, it significantly impacts clinical outcomes. Antimicrobial-resistant NTS infections often lead to more severe illness, prolonged hospitalization, increased treatment failure rates, and a higher risk of mortality.

History of *Salmonella*

Salmonella has a rich history dating back to the 1800s. In 1888, the successful cultivation of the organism was achieved by Salmon and Smith, while Gartner reported the initial human case and isolation of the bacteria.³¹ The nomenclature "*Salmonella*" was established in 1900, a tribute to its discovery in the laboratory of Daniel Elmer Salmon.³² Since then, significant confusion among strains has been observed in relation to the large number of isolated *Salmonella* strains. Only the detailed study of antigens has made possible the valid identification and classification of strains. The serological study describes the O and H antigens of *Salmonella*, enabling precise identification of the bacterium.³³ In 1926, Bruce White presented the first outline of the antigenic structure of *Salmonella* species. White's research was taken up and expanded by Kauffmann (1941), who developed the Kauffmann-White Scheme, the basis for all studies in the field of *Salmonella*. This scheme has gained general agreement from the scientific community. This scheme gives each known strain of *Salmonella* to date a distinct identity.³³⁻³⁶

The update of this scheme is the responsibility of the World Health Organization Collaborating Centre for Reference and Research on *Salmonella*, OMS-Salm (Pasteur Institute, Paris, France), in collaboration with the World Health Organization (WHO). New serotypes are continually documented in the list of the Kauffmann-White-Le Minor scheme,^{35,36} last updated, to the best of our knowledge, in 2014.³⁶

Bacteriological characteristics

Belonging to the Enterobacteriaceae family, *Salmonella* is characterized by consistent morphological and biochemical features. The bacilli typically measure between 2 to 5 µm in length and 0.7 to 1.5 µm in width. *Salmonella* is Gram-negative, oxidase-negative and the majority of its strains display motility, facilitated by peritrichous flagella, produces gas from glucose and exhibit

the ability to reduce nitrates to nitrites.^{37,31} In general, the biochemical characteristics of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* serotypes are as follows: lactose-, ONPG-, H₂S+, LDC+, ODC+, urease-, indole-, gelatinase-, DNase-, Simmons citrate-, adonitol-, glycerol-, galacturonate-. Some phenotypic properties of *Salmonella* are so specific that they are used for the enrichment, selection, isolation, and differentiation of colonies. *Salmonella* and other Enterobacteriaceae are resistant to novobiocin, selenite, tergitol, and bile salts, especially deoxycholate. The most selective media such as the *Salmonella*-Shigella (S.S) medium, contains bile salts and brilliant green as selection agents, lactose and sodium thiosulfate as substrates, and neutral red and ferric citrates as indicators. *Salmonella* strains typically yield colonies (usually with a diameter of 2 to 4 mm) with a black center (indicating the presence of H₂S). As a mesophilic bacterium, *Salmonella* grows at temperatures close to the body temperature of warm-blooded animals (35-43°C), with an optimal pH of 7.2.^{38,37,31}

Taxonomy and nomenclature

The nomenclature of *Salmonella* is particularly complex as it has been the subject of controversies and confusion over time. Before 1973, Kauffmann proposed the idea that a serovar is equivalent to a species.^{39,35} However, in 1973, DNA-DNA hybridization revealed the connection of all serovars at the species level, with *Salmonella bongori* as the exception.⁴⁰ The nomenclature shift led to recognizing two *Salmonella* species: *Salmonella bongori* and *Salmonella enterica*, with the latter having six subspecies (*enterica*, *salamae*, *arizonae*, *diarizonae*, *houtenae*, and *indica*).³⁶ In fact, Le Minor and Popoff's proposal avoided confusion between species and serovar names. They proposed not to consider the names of serovars as Latin names, to write them with an initial capital letter (for example, *Salmonella enterica* subsp. *enterica* serovar *enteritidis*). In common practice and to simplify the nomenclature, Le Minor and Popoff also proposed to designate serovars in an abbreviated form: *Salmonella enteritidis*.⁴¹ The way *Salmonella* serotypes have been designated has evolved over time. Bacteriologists used to name them after the diseases they caused or the animal species from which the bacillus originated. This is how we have *Salmonella gallinarum*, *Salmonella abortusovis*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, etc. However, the designation of new serovars is based exclusively on the geographical origin.^{35,42} Until the 2000s, 2463 serovars were identified, including 1454 belonging to the *enterica* species and 20 to

the *bongori* species. In 2014, the Kauffmann-White-Le Minor scheme recognized 2,659 serotypes, with 1,586 under the *enterica* species and 22 under *bongori*.³⁶

Multi-drug resistant MDR *Salmonella*

A noticeable rise in multi-resistant strains has been observed, limiting treatment options and leading to heightened morbidity and mortality rates. In recent years, there have been concerning trends in the development of antimicrobial resistance among *Salmonella* strains, posing a significant public health challenge. From the 1950s onwards, the emergence of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* strains with decreased susceptibility to various antibiotic classes has been observed. The emergence of antimicrobial resistance is a common trend among bacterial pathogens that contaminate food animals, as these drugs are often used as growth promoters.^{43,44} Indeed, the emergence of resistant bacteria can be attributed to the inappropriate use of antimicrobial agents especially in agriculture,⁴⁵ a concern that is particularly pronounced in developing countries.⁴⁶ It has often followed the use of multiple antibiotic classes in animals which contributes to the selection of resistant strains and their subsequent spread.^{46,47} For example, the use of fluoroquinolones in chicken flocks can shift or replace bacteria from 100% susceptible to 100% resistant within a few days.⁴⁸ The use of third-generation cephalosporins can also be associated with the emergence of particularly concerning *Salmonella* strains due to their resistance to these antimicrobials.^{49,50} The misuse or overuse of third-generation cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones in both human medicine and agriculture has led to the development of multidrug-resistant (MDR) *Salmonella* resisting not only cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones but also multiple other classes of antibiotics. These powerful antibiotics, while effective against a range of bacterial infections, can drive the selection of resistant strains among bacteria like *Salmonella*. Furthermore, ESBL (extended-spectrum Beta-Lactamase) producing strains, expressing resistance to the broad range of antibiotics; beta-lactams, are increasingly identified in *Salmonella* isolates.⁵¹ NTS has also shown signs of acquired resistance to colistin, an antibiotic of last-line defence against several MDR bacteria.⁵² Resistance to these potent drugs limits the available treatment options and can result in higher rates of treatment failure and complications.

To address these trends, there is a growing emphasis on *Salmonella* antimicrobial surveillance programs. Data provided by surveillance organizations show varying levels

of bacterial resistance in different countries, due to differences in prescribing practices of antibiotics to animals destined for human consumption by farmers. However, due to the globalization of trade, multi-resistant strains are easily disseminated worldwide.⁴⁸ As a result of these dissemination patterns, it becomes crucial to understand how antibiotic resistance can emerge, either through mutations within bacterial populations or via the acquisition of resistance determinants through horizontal gene transfer mechanisms. The widespread use of antibiotics in natural habitats truly challenges the microbial populations in these ecosystems.^{46,48} Research efforts are focused on understanding the genetic mechanisms underlying resistance and developing new strategies for combating drug-resistant bacteria.

Pathogenicity of *Salmonella* and virulence factors

Salmonella possess various virulence factors that allow the bacteria to adapt to environmental conditions and host responses at each stage of the infection process. Research has led to the discovery of unique protein secretion systems controlling the key steps of infection, such as invading epithelial cells and surviving within macrophages. *Salmonella* infections typically originate in the intestine. After colonization, the bacteria multiply in the digestive tract, with the cecum serving as a crucial site for their replication. After transient bacteremia, the bacteria could be found in regional lymph nodes and within the liver and spleen macrophages, organs that *Salmonella* have a particular affinity for. *Salmonella* can multiply within these organs before being disseminated through the bloodstream. In immunocompromised individuals, serotypes responsible for gastroenteritis in humans can enter the reticuloendothelial system and cause severe systemic disease. During gastroenteritis, the symptoms are partly related to the secretion of an enterotoxin but primarily due to the destruction of villi, disrupting absorption functions, and significant inflammation that increases secretions. In cases of septicemia, the endotoxin released from bacterial lysis is responsible for toxic shock.⁵³

The outcome of a *Salmonella* infection largely depends on the virulence of the specific strain and the host's status. While factors like age, genetics, and the environment primarily determine the host's condition, the bacteria's characteristics are determined by virulence factors.⁵⁴ Several *Salmonella* virulence factors have been identified, including type III secretion systems, the Vi antigen, the lipopolysaccharides, the flagella, and various other factors

essential for the intracellular life cycle of the strain.⁵⁵ The genes encoding these factors are typically located on *Salmonella* Pathogenicity Islands (SPI).⁵⁵ SPIs are extensive regions of DNA inserted into the chromosome. They are defined as DNA segments encoding virulence genes. This DNA region is absent from the corresponding region in the genome of *E. coli* K12, which is known to be roughly colinear with the *Salmonella typhimurium* chromosome.⁵⁵ Key regions of SPIs are postulated to have played a major role in the divergence between *Salmonella* and *E. coli* over millions of years and appear to contribute to the adaptation of *Salmonella* to its hosts.⁵⁵ SPIs, of varying lengths, often carry large groups of genes contributing to a specific virulence phenotype.⁵⁶ The first pathogenicity island, SPI1, governs the ability of *Salmonella* to invade host epithelial cells through a type III secretion system. The second island, SPI2, controls the pathogen's survival in macrophages through a distinct type III secretion system. The major virulence factor of SPI3 is a system necessary for survival in the face of intramacrophage nutritional limitations.⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹ The invasion function in *Salmonella* is not solely controlled by SPI1; genes from SPI4 also play a crucial role.⁶⁰ In general, more than 20 SPIs are identified in *Salmonella*, from which islands 1, 2, and 4 are potentially conserved within the genus, while the others are variable or partially variable.^{59,61}

Next generation sequencing in *Salmonella*

The advent of Next Generation Sequencing technologies has revolutionized pathogen surveillance as rapid and efficient techniques enabling the comprehensive analysis of a bacterium's complete DNA sequence.¹⁵ The transformative impact of NGS on enteric pathogen monitoring is now evident in public health laboratories, where it is replacing the reliance on multiple independent laboratory tests.²⁸ As the cost of these technologies is decreasing and run times are becoming more efficient and allows for the inference of a wide range of pathogen features in a single sequencing run, the techniques are expected to become more widely available in routine diagnostic laboratories.^{28,62} In addition, recent applications in metagenome sequencing for infectious disease diagnosis and outbreak investigation demonstrate the potential for culture-independent pathogen detection from complex clinical samples. The speed of sequencing, the direct extraction of serovar and multilocus sequence typing information from genome data facilitates the linkage of sequenced isolates to historical data, enabling the rapid

tracing of the origin of contamination sources.^{63,64} The primary analyses employed for these purposes include single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) analysis, based on the detection of variations in single nucleotide positions in the genome, core genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST), involving a gene-by-gene examination using only core genes, and whole-genome MLST (wgMLST), which encompasses MLST by using both core and accessory genes.⁶³⁻⁶⁸

Given the inconsistency of traditional molecular typing methods, Multilocus Sequence Typing (MLST) emerged as a more reliable and standardized approach for characterizing bacterial strains.⁶⁹ The MLST strategy aims to pinpoint internal nucleotide sequences of specific housekeeping genes, typically ranging from 400 to 500 base pairs. This approach assigns a unique "allelic profile," constituting a distinct set of alleles at each locus, to designate the sequence type (ST). MLST emerged when robotic sequencers made it possible to determine nucleotide sequences of a group of housekeeping genes, ribosomal genes, and/or virulence genes.^{69,70} MLST has the capability to assess sequence changes at the level of a single nucleotide.⁶⁹ Since its inception, MLST, pioneered with the Neisseria scheme, has earned the status of the "gold standard" in typing. Subsequently, species-specific schemes for various bacteria and fungi have proliferated. The curated databases housing ST profiles and MLST allele sequences are globally dispersed.^{71,72} Beyond its role in outbreak scenarios, MLST serves to categorize isolates across different species globally.^{73,74} In diverse bacterial applications, the accurate and consistent classification of bacteria is paramount. Swift and precise identification of infectious agent strains is crucial, particularly during outbreaks.^{73,74} When needed, MLST, alongside other genetic subtyping techniques, contributes a phylogenetic context within a serotype, a crucial facet in public health surveillance. The advent of cutting-edge technologies, such as Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS), facilitates the integration of identification, subtyping, and characterization workflows into a singular, comprehensive platform.⁶⁵

The current era of high-throughput sequencing advocates for using Whole Genome Sequence (WGS) data for typing. The decreasing cost of DNA sequencing, technological advancements, and equipment cost savings render WGS affordable for individual researchers and routine laboratories. The higher quantity of complete MLST profiles obtained using WGS based approaches than with

the traditional method is proof of their superiority.⁷⁵ Multilocus Sequence Typing (MLST), which indicates to be an effective method for characterizing bacterial isolates, has been made more versatile by WGS strategies to accommodate high-throughput data.⁷⁶ The accessibility of WGS for routine laboratories opens avenues for trend research, diagnoses, and surveillance, promising quick completion times conducive to real-time surveillance and epidemic detection.⁶³ However, challenges lie in sifting through voluminous data and connecting WGS to typing schemes, enabling comparisons with other widely used technologies and historical data.

Next generation sequencing-related techniques are not only useful for identifying bacteria at different levels of classification but also allow studying genetic markers, such as those for virulence and antibiotic resistance. Understanding these markers is crucial for gaining insights into the pathogenesis of bacteria, the mechanisms behind resistance to antibiotics, and the epidemiology of infectious diseases.

Detection of virulence genes

Virulence factors enable bacteria to infect and cause illness in their hosts. These factors are crucial for bacterial infections, playing a key role in helping bacteria to evade or counteract the host's immune defense. They are vital for researching bacterial diseases and creating treatments.⁷⁷ Next-genome sequencing technologies have significantly advanced the studies on virulence markers in bacteria. Three main methodologies are used for the identification of virulence genes in bacterial genomes.⁷⁸⁻⁸¹ The first one is based on the comparison of genomes from strains with different virulence levels. It involves analyzing the genetic differences between highly virulent and less virulent strains. Tools like BLAST can be used for the alignment and the comparison of the genomes in order to identify differences in sequences associated to virulence. This method is commonly used in microbial genomics.^{78,79,82} The second method involves the identification of laterally transferred genomic islands, and running the genome against databases of known virulence markers. This methodology considers virulence genes as being acquired via gene transfer. Software like Island Viewer integrates various genomic island prediction methods to identify potential horizontally acquired regions in genomes.⁷⁸ The third strategy proceeds with running the Genome against databases of Known virulence markers: This involves comparing a genome to existing databases to identify known virulence genes.

Databases such as VFDB (Virulence Factor Database) are used in conjunction with tools like BLAST to identify known virulence genes in genomic sequences.^{1,78}

Detection of resistance genes

Antimicrobial resistance poses a major worldwide health challenge, particularly in bacteria with decreased susceptibility to strong antibiotics like third-generation cephalosporins and carbapenems.⁸³ NGS allows the prediction of bacterial resistance types, even those not typically assessed through conventional antimicrobial tests. It enables real-time creation of antimicrobial resistance profiles and prediction of multi-resistant pathogens such as *Salmonella*.^{28,65,84} In recent years, various methods and tools have been developed and published for detecting genetic factors responsible for antimicrobial resistance. These tools analyze data obtained from whole-genome sequencing (WGS) aiding in the comprehensive identification and understanding of resistance mechanisms.⁸⁵

Generally, the methods used for finding resistance markers are similar to those used for detecting virulence genes. Three primary methods are available for identifying resistance genes. Genomic comparisons between resistant and susceptible strains are conducted using genomic alignments and comparisons tools such as BLAST. Resistance genes are also identified by comparing genomic sequences with established databases like CARD (Comprehensive Antibiotic Resistance Database), Resfinder, ARDB (Antibiotic Resistance Genes Database), ARG-ANNOT (Antibiotic Resistance Gene-ANNOTation) and MEGARes (MEtaGenome Analyzer for Antimicrobial Resistance) to identify known resistance genes in genomic sequences along with with the use of alignment tools.^{28,86,87} The analysis of mutations conferring resistance with tools such as BWA, Samtools, or PointFinder also enables researchers to understand antimicrobial resistance mechanisms.^{28,86,87} These emerging methods serve as valuable additions to conventional culture-based approaches in clinical and surveillance settings. They offer rapid and precise means to determine resistance in both cultivable and non-cultivable bacteria.^{79,85}

Surveillance, Outbreaks & phylogenetic Investigations:

Next generation sequencing has proven to be an essential tool in epidemiology, enabling detailed analysis of infectious disease transmission. It has been particularly effective in tracking micro-epidemics and understanding the spread of diseases globally. Combined with

bioinformatics, it revolutionizing *Salmonella* outbreak surveillance. During infectious outbreaks, this approach enables precise and rapid identification of the involved strains. By comparing genomic sequences, researchers can trace infection sources, track disease spread, and establish connections among related cases. This tracing capability significantly enhances epidemiological investigations, enabling a swift response to contain disease dissemination. Moreover, this method establishes connections among bacterial strains from different geographical regions, aiding in understanding transmission patterns and anticipating risks of nationwide or even international spread. It plays a crucial role in managing public health emergencies and devising effective public health strategies to control *Salmonella* outbreaks. These technologies have enhanced outbreak detection by identifying outbreaks even with a smaller number of cases.⁸⁸⁻⁹³ Moreover, it has significantly improved the ability to establish connections between human illnesses and specific infection sources. In this revelation, NGS presents opportunities to address inquiries regarding foodborne pathogens and potential preventive measures that were previously unattainable.⁹⁰ Whole genome sequencing WGS was first applied to investigate a severe listeriosis outbreak in Canada. The investigation involved two outbreak-related isolates with close PFGE patterns. WGS enabled a comprehensive genetic comparison, revealing distinct strains potentially contributing to the outbreak. Many studies showcased NGS techniques as valuable tools applicable in urgent public health crises.^{94,95} Since then, the consistent integration of NGS into disease surveillance has notably strengthened our capabilities in identifying and investigating outbreaks, as well as in tracking disease patterns.

The American national surveillance network for foodborne disease PulseNet, which controls subtyping of *Salmonella* and other bacteria, used to perform pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) as a standard method for molecular subtyping, until 2015. Then, laboratories introduced WGS and collected sequences data to standardize genotypic serotyping by SeqSero (<http://www.denglab.info/SeqSero>). The PulseNet database is using core genome MLST (cgMLST) and Single-nucleotide polymorphism SNP analysis to exhibit the phylogenetic relationships of the bacterial isolates. Antimicrobial resistance is also studied by predicting antimicrobial resistance determinants using in silico tools such as ResFinder.⁹⁶

In silico and Bioinformatics Tools:

The assembly of the *Salmonella* genome is a fundamental step involving reconstructing the complete genome sequence from raw sequencing data. In silico genome assembly from sequencing data process DNA fragments to accurately and exhaustively reconstruct the bacterial genome sequence.^{97,98} This step is crucial for identifying specific genes, coding regions, and functional elements within the *Salmonella* genome. As for annotation, it represents the process of identifying and characterizing genes and functionalities within the assembled genome. Annotation tools automatically annotate genes based on their presumed function. These annotations are valuable for understanding the roles of genes in pathogenicity, drug resistance, and other biological characteristics of *Salmonella*.^{99,100} The evolution of in silico tools in Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) has seen significant progress driven by computational advancements. Early tools struggled with short-read sequencing but gradually improved with novel algorithms. With the rise of long-read sequencing, new tools, offering better handling of longer reads and more accurate assembly. Hybrid approaches combining short and long reads further enhanced accuracy and contiguity. Ongoing advancements prioritize speed, accuracy, and scalability, refining algorithms to handle large datasets efficiently while improving genome assembly's precision and completeness.^{101,102} Specialized bioinformatics tools like ResFinder, CARD, VFDB, or Victors are designed to detect genes associated with antimicrobial resistance and virulence factors within *Salmonella* genomes. These tools use genetic data to predict potential virulence and antimicrobial resistance and identify the corresponding contributors and mechanisms. The latter provides crucial information to understand disease dynamics and adapt treatment strategies. By identifying resistance genes in *Salmonella* strains, these tools help anticipate resistance profiles and guide treatment choices, contributing to a more targeted and effective approach to combat infections.¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁵ The development of such tools makes food safety research shifting away from traditional molecular subtyping approaches toward NGS-based characterization methods.

CONCLUSION

In summary, Next generation sequencing technologies such as whole genome sequencing have revolutionized the field of microbiology, particularly in food safety and public

health. These technologies provide unparalleled insights into the genetic content of pathogens which enhances the understanding of disease transmission and tracking. As NGS evolves, it promises to become an even more integral tool in microbiological research and outbreak response, with potential applications expanding into more efficient, high-resolution typing for a wide range of bacterial strains. Overall, globally, food safety surveillance knows a transitional phase from traditional molecular subtyping to next-generation sequencing methods since it can identify rapidly and with high precision genotypes, virulence factors, antibiotic resistance, and phylogenetic relationships of the bacterial strains, replacing conventional tests, especially for hard-to-grow microorganisms. However, challenges related to the practical limitations of its implementation, like the need for sophisticated data interpretation, regular database updates, and advanced software persist, especially within developing countries.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed to the concept of the study. Anubha Kumari- Conceptualization, writing-original draft Validation writing, review and editing; Amal Ben Hassena: Resources review Analysis, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization and editing; Anjali Kumari: validation of the work Software and review and editing of the draft; Avinash Kumar: Supervision, Validation writing, review and editing. All authors approved the final version submitted for publication and take responsibility for the statements made in the review.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

DATA SHARING STATEMENTS

The review is based on the references cited. All data generated and analyzed during the study are included in this published article and the citations herein. Further details opinions and interpretation are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

REFERENCES

1. **Hassena Amal Ben, Julie Haendiges, Sonia Zormati, Sonda Guerhazi, Radhouane Gdoura, Narjol Gonzalez-Escalona, and Mariam Siala 2021.** Virulence and resistance genes profiles and clonal relationships of non-typhoidal food-borne *Salmonella* strains isolated in Tunisia by whole genome sequencing. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*. **337**: 108941.
2. **Qamar Farah Naz, Wajid Hussain, and Sonia Qureshi 2022.** Salmonellosis including enteric fever. *Pediatric Clinics*. **69(1)**: 65-77.
3. **Oludairo Oladapo O., Jacob KP Kwaga, Junaid Kabir, Paul A. Abdu, Arya Gitanjali, Ann Perrets, Veronica Cibin, Antonia Lettini, and Julius Aiyedun 2022.** A review on *Salmonella* characteristics, taxonomy, nomenclature with special reference to non-Typhoidal and Typhoidal salmonellosis. *Zagazig Veterinary Journal*. **50(2)**: 161-176.
4. **Gal-Mor, Ohad, Erin C. Boyle, and Guntram A. Grassl. 2014.** Same species, different diseases: how and why typhoidal and non-typhoidal *Salmonella enterica* serovars differ. *Frontiers in microbiology*. **5**: 391.
5. **Popa, Gabriela Loredana, and Mircea Ioan Papa 2021.** *Salmonella* spp. infection-a continuous threat worldwide. *Germes*. **11(1)**: 88.
6. **Adesiji Yemisi O., Vijaya Kumar Deekshit, and Indrani Karunasagar.** "Antimicrobial resistant genes associated with *Salmonella* spp. isolated from human, poultry, and seafood sources. *Food science & nutrition*. **2(4)**: 436-442.
7. **Michael G. B., and S. Schwarz 2014.** Antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic nontyphoidal *Salmonella*: an alarming trend?. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*. **22(12)**: 968-974.
8. **Wan Makhtar, Wan Ratmaazila, Izwan Bharudin, Nurul Hidayah Samsulrizal, and Nik Yusnoraini Yusof. 2021.** Whole genome sequencing analysis of *Salmonella enterica* serovar typhi: history and current approaches. *Microorganisms*. **9(10)**: 2155.
9. **Barbour, Elie K., Danielle B. Ayyash, Wafa Alturkistni, Areej Alyahiby, Soonham Yaghamoor,**

- Archana Iyer, Jehad Yousef, Taha Kumosani, and Steve Harakeh 2015. Impact of sporadic reporting of poultry *Salmonella serovars* from selected developing countries. *The Journal of Infection in Developing Countries*. **9(01)**: 001-007.
10. Belina, Dinaol, Yonas Hailu, Tesfaye Gobena, Tine Hald, and Patrick Murigu Kamau Njage 2021. Prevalence and epidemiological distribution of selected foodborne pathogens in human and different environmental samples in Ethiopia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *One health outlook*. **3(1)**: 19.
 11. Yopa Daniele Sandra, Douglas Mbang Massom, Gbètogo Maxime Kiki, Ramde Wendkoaghenda Sophie, Sylvie Fasine, Oumou Thiam, Lassane Zinaba, and Patrice Ngangue. 2023. Barriers and enablers to the implementation of one health strategies in developing countries: a systematic review. *Frontiers in public health*. **11**: 1252428.
 12. Aleksandrowicz Adrianna, Ewa Carolak, Agata Dutkiewicz, Aleksandra Blachut, Wiktoria Waszczuk, and Krzysztof Grzymajlo 2023. Better together–*Salmonella* biofilm-associated antibiotic resistance. *Gut Microbes*. **15(1)**: 2229937.
 13. Peykov Slavil, and Tanya Strateva 2023. Whole-genome sequencing-based resistome analysis of nosocomial multidrug-resistant non-fermenting Gram-negative pathogens from the Balkans. *Microorganisms*. **11(3)**: 651.
 14. Bianconi Irene, Richard Aschbacher, and Elisabetta Pagani 2023. Current uses and future perspectives of genomic technologies in clinical microbiology. *Antibiotics*. **12(11)**: 1580.
 15. Thomas Milton, Gavin John Fenske, Linto Antony, Sudeep Ghimire, Ronald Welsh, Akhilesh Ramachandran, and Joy Scaria 2017. Whole genome sequencing-based detection of antimicrobial resistance and virulence in non-typhoidal *Salmonella enterica* isolated from wildlife. *Gut pathogens*. **9**:1-9.
 16. Kwong Jason C., N. McCallum, Vitali Sintchenko, and Benjamin P. Howden 2015. Whole genome sequencing in clinical and public health microbiology. *Pathology*. **47(3)**: 199-210.
 17. Ferrari, Rafaela G., Denes KA Rosario, Adelino Cunha-Neto, Sérgio B. Mano, Eduardo ES Figueiredo, and Carlos A. Conte-Junior 2019. Worldwide epidemiology of *Salmonella serovars* in animal-based foods: a meta-analysis. *Applied and environmental microbiology*. **85(14)**: e00591-19.
 18. Ehuwa Olugbenga, Amit K. Jaiswal, and Swarna Jaiswal. 2021. Food Safety and Food Handling Practices.
 19. Majowicz Shannon E., Jennie Musto, Elaine Scallan, Frederick J. Angulo, Martyn Kirk, Sarah J. O'Brien, Timothy F. Jones, Aamir Fazil, Robert M. Hoekstra, and International Collaboration on Enteric Disease “Burden of Illness” Studies 2010. The global burden of nontyphoidal *Salmonella gastroenteritis*. *Clinical infectious diseases*. **50(6)**: 882-889.
 20. ÝNCE, Seyyide SARIÇAM, and A. K. A. N. Mehmet 2023. Molecular characterization of virulence genes in poultry-originated *Salmonella enteritidis* and *Salmonella typhimurium*. *Ankara Üniversitesi Veteriner Fakültesi Dergisi*. 1-6.
 21. Marchello Christian S., Megan Birkhold, John A. Crump, Laura B. Martin, Michael O. Ansah, Gianluca Breggi, Rocio Canals 2022. Complications and mortality of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* invasive disease: a global systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. **22(5)**: 692-705.
 22. Phu Huong Lan, Nguyen, Tu Le Thi Phuong, Hien Nguyen Huu, Le Thuy, Alison E. Mather, Se Eun Park, Florian Marks 2016. Invasive non-typhoidal *Salmonella* infections in Asia: clinical observations, disease outcome and dominant serovars from an infectious disease hospital in Vietnam. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*. **10(8)**: e0004857.
 23. Marchello, Christian S., Fabio Fiorino, Elena Pettini, John A. Crump, Laura B. Martin, Gianluca Breggi, Rocio Canals 2021. Incidence of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* invasive disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Infection*. **83(5)**: 523-532.

24. **Stanaway Jeffrey D., Andrea Parisi, Kaushik Sarkar, Brigitte F. Blacker, Robert C. Reiner, Simon I. Hay, Molly R. Nixon 2019.** The global burden of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* invasive disease: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. **19(12)**: 1312-1324.
25. **Uche Ifeanyi Valentine, Calman A. MacLennan, and Allan Saul 2017.** A systematic review of the incidence, risk factors and case fatality rates of invasive nontyphoidal *Salmonella* (iNTS) disease in Africa (1966 to 2014).” *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*. **11(1)**: e0005118.
26. **Reddy Elizabeth A., Andrea V. Shaw, and John A. Crump 2010.** Community-acquired bloodstream infections in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet infectious diseases*. **10(6)**: 417-432.
27. **Marchello Christian S., Ariella P. Dale, Sruti Pisharody, Matthew P. Rubach, and John A. Crump 2019.** A systematic review and meta-analysis of the prevalence of community-onset bloodstream infections among hospitalized patients in Africa and Asia. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy*. **64(1)**: 10-1128.
28. **Neuert Saskia, Sathesh Nair, Martin R. Day, Michel Doumith, Philip M. Ashton, Kate C. Mellor, Claire Jenkins 2018.** Prediction of phenotypic antimicrobial resistance profiles from whole genome sequences of non-typhoidal *Salmonella enterica*. *Frontiers in microbiology*. **9**: 592.
29. **Majowicz Shannon E., Jennie Musto, Elaine Scallan, Frederick J. Angulo, Martyn Kirk, Sarah J. O’Brien, Timothy F. Jones, Aamir Fazil, Robert M. Hoekstra, and International Collaboration on Enteric Disease “Burden of Illness” Studies 2010.** The global burden of nontyphoidal *Salmonella gastroenteritis*. *Clinical infectious diseases*. **50(6)**: 882-889.
30. **Crump John A., Tonney S. Nyirenda, Lisette Mbuyi Kalonji, Marie-France Phoba, Bieke Tack, James A. Platts-Mills, Melita A. Gordon, and Samuel M. Kariuki 2023.** Nontyphoidal *Salmonella* invasive disease: challenges and solutions. In *Open forum infectious diseases*, **10(1)**: S32-S37. US: Oxford University Press.
31. **Oludairo Oladapo O., Jacob KP Kwaga, Junaid Kabir, Paul A. Abdu, Arya Gitanjali, Ann Perrets, Veronica Cibin, Antonia Lettini, and Julius Aiyedun 2022.** A review on *Salmonella* characteristics, taxonomy, nomenclature with special reference to non-Typhoidal and Typhoidal salmonellosis. *Zagazig Veterinary Journal*. **50(2)**: 161-176.
32. **Su L., and C. H. Chiu 2007.** *Salmonella*: clinical importance and evolution of nomenclature. *Chang Gung medical journal*. **30(3)**: 210.
33. **Rycroft, Andrew N 2000.** Structure, function and synthesis of surface polysaccharides in *Salmonella*. 19-33.
34. **Ghysels G 1964.** Les Salmonelloses: 80 ans d’Histoire. The World Problem of Salmonellosis, 9-18
35. **Brenner F. W., R. G. Villar, F. J. Angulo, R. Tauxe, and B. Swaminathan 2000.** *Salmonella* nomenclature. *Journal of clinical microbiology*. **38(7)**: 2465-2467.
36. **Issenhuth-Jeanjean Sylvie, Peter Roggentin, Matthew Mikoleit, Martine Guibourdenche, Elizabeth De Pinna, Sathesh Nair, Patricia I. Fields, and François-Xavier Weill. 2014.** Supplement 2008–2010 (no. 48) to the white–Kauffmann–Le minor scheme.” *Research in microbiology*. **165(7)**: 526-530.
37. **Korsak N., J-N. Degeye, Grégory Etienne, Bernard China, and Georges Daube 2004.** Comparison of four different methods for *Salmonella* detection in fecal samples of porcine origin. *Journal of food protection*. **67(10)**: 2158-2164.
38. **Grimont Patrick AD, Francine Grimont, and Philippe Bouvet. 2000.** Taxonomy of the genus *Salmonella*. 1-17.
39. **Kauffmann F., and P. R. Edwards 1952.** Classification and nomenclature of Enterobacteriaceae. 2-8.
40. **Crosa J. H., D. J. Brenner, W. H. Ewing, and S. Falkow 1973.** Molecular relationships among the Salmonelleae. *Journal of bacteriology*. **115(1)**: 307-315.

41. **Le Minor, Leon, and Michel Y. Popoff 1987.** Request for an opinion: Designation of *Salmonella enterica* sp. nov., nom. rev., as the type and only species of the genus *Salmonella*. *International journal of systematic and evolutionary microbiology*. **37(4)**: 465-468.
42. **Tindall B. J., P. A. D. Grimont, G. M. Garrity, and J. P. Euzéby 2005.** Nomenclature and taxonomy of the genus *Salmonella*. *International journal of systematic and evolutionary microbiology*. **55(1)**: 521-524.
43. **Salam Md Abdus, Md Yusuf Al-Amin, Moushumi Tabassoom Salam, Jogendra Singh Pawar, Naseem Akhter, Ali A. Rabaan, and Mohammed AA Alqumber 2023.** Antimicrobial resistance: a growing serious threat for global public health. *In Healthcare*. **11(13)**:1946. MDPI.
44. **Aslam Bilal, Wei Wang, Muhammad Imran Arshad, Mohsin Khurshid, Saima Muzammil, Muhammad Hidayat Rasool, Muhammad Atif Nisar 2018.** Antibiotic resistance: a rundown of a global crisis. *Infection and drug resistance*. 1645-1658.
45. **Tauxe Robert V 2002.** Emerging foodborne pathogens. *International journal of food microbiology*. **78(1-2)**: 31-41.
46. **Ventola C. Lee 2015.** The antibiotic resistance crisis: part 1: causes and threats. *Pharmacy and therapeutics* **40(4)**: 277.
47. **Weill F. X. 2008.** Zoonotic non-typhi *Salmonella* and antibiotic resistance. *Bulletin de l'Académie Vétérinaire de France*. **161(3)**: 221.
48. **Alcaine Samuel D., Lorin D. Warnick, and Martin Wiedmann 2007.** Antimicrobial resistance in nontyphoidal *Salmonella*. *Journal of food protection*. **70(3)**: 780-790.
49. **Dunne Eileen F., Paul D. Fey, Pat Kludt, Roshan Reporter, Farzad Mostashari, Pam Shillam, Julie Wicklund 2000.** Emergence of domestically acquired ceftriaxone-resistant *Salmonella* infections associated with AmpC β -lactamase." *Jama* **284(24)**: 3151-3156.
50. **Manyi-Loh Christy, Sampson Mamphweli, Edson Meyer, and Anthony Okoh 2018.** Characterisation and antibiotic resistance of selected bacterial pathogens recovered from dairy cattle manure during anaerobic mono-digestion in a balloon-type digester. *Applied Sciences*. **8(11)**: 2088.
51. **Terreni Marco, Marina Taccani, and Massimo Pregnolato 2021.** New antibiotics for multidrug-resistant bacterial strains: latest research developments and future perspectives. *Molecules* **26(9)**: 2671.
52. **Sharma Jyotsana, Nanjundappa Manjunatha, Somnath S. Pokhare, Prakash G. Patil, Ruchi Agarrwal, Mansi G. Chakranarayan, Anita Aralimar, Priya Devagire, and Rajiv A. Marathe 2022.** Genetic diversity and streptomycin sensitivity in *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *punicae* causing oily spot disease in pomegranates. *Horticulturae*. **8(5)**: 441.
53. **Millemann, Y 1998.** Pathogenic power of Salmonellae: virulence factors and study models. *Veterinary Research*. **29(5)**: 385-407.
54. **van Asten, Alphons JAM, and Jaap E. van Dijk 2005.** Distribution of "classic" virulence factors among *Salmonella* spp. *FEMS immunology & medical microbiology*. **44(3)**: 251-259.
55. **Fierer Joshua, and Donald G. Guiney 2001.** "Diverse virulence traits underlying different clinical outcomes of *Salmonella* infection. *The Journal of clinical investigation*. **107(7)**: 775-780.
56. **Ochman Howard, and Eduardo A. Groisman 1996.** Distribution of pathogenicity islands in *Salmonella* spp. *Infection and immunity*. **64(12)**: 5410-5412.
57. **Groisman Eduardo A., and Howard Ochman 1993.** Cognate gene clusters govern invasion of host epithelial cells by *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Shigella flexneri*. *The EMBO Journal*. **12(10)**: 3779-3787.
58. **Ochman Howard, Fernando C. Soncini, Felix Solomon, and Eduardo A. Groisman 1996.** Identification of a pathogenicity island required for *Salmonella* survival in host cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. **93(15)**: 7800-7804.
59. **Hensel Michael. 2004.** Evolution of pathogenicity islands of *Salmonella enterica*. *International Journal of Medical Microbiology*. **294(2-3)**: 95-102.
60. **Gerlach Roman G., Daniela Jackel, Nina Geymeier, and Michael Hensel 2007.** *Salmonella* pathogenicity island 4-mediated adhesion is coregulated with

- invasion genes in *Salmonella enterica*. *Infection and immunity*. **75(10)**: 4697-4709.
61. De Jong, Hanna K., Chris M. Parry, Tom van der Poll, and W. Joost Wiersinga. 2012. Host–pathogen interaction in invasive salmonellosis. e1002933.
 62. Larsen Mette V., Salvatore Cosentino, Simon Rasmussen, Carsten Friis, Henrik Hasman, Rasmus Lykke Marvig, Lars Jelsbak 2012. Multilocus sequence typing of total-genome-sequenced bacteria. *Journal of clinical microbiology*. **50(4)**: 1355-1361.
 63. Den Bakker, Henk C., Marc W. Allard, Dianna Bopp, Eric W. Brown, John Fontana, Zamin Iqbal, Aristeo Kinney 2014. Rapid whole-genome sequencing for surveillance of *Salmonella enterica* serovar enteritidis. *Emerging infectious diseases*. **20(8)**: 1306.
 64. Zhang Shaokang, Yanlong Yin, Marcus B. Jones, Zhenzhen Zhang, Brooke L. Deatherage Kaiser, Blake A. Dinsmore, Collette Fitzgerald, Patricia I. Fields, and Xiangyu Deng. 2015. *Salmonella* serotype determination utilizing high-throughput genome sequencing data. *Journal of clinical microbiology*. **53(5)**: 1685-1692.
 65. Katz Lee S., Taylor Griswold, Amanda J. Williams-Newkirk, Darlene Wagner, Aaron Petkau, Cameron Sieffert, Gary Van Domselaar, Xiangyu Deng, and Heather A. Carleton 2017. A comparative analysis of the Lyve-SET phylogenomics pipeline for genomic epidemiology of foodborne pathogens. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. **8**: 375.
 66. Yachison Chris A., Catherine Yoshida, James Robertson, John HE Nash, Peter Kruczkiewicz, Eduardo N. Taboada, Matthew Walker. 2017. The validation and implications of using whole genome sequencing as a replacement for traditional serotyping for a national *Salmonella* reference laboratory. *Frontiers in microbiology*. **8**: 1044.
 67. Jagadeesan Balamurugan, Peter Gerner-Smidt, Marc W. Allard, Sébastien Leuillet, Anett Winkler, Yinghua Xiao, Samuel Chaffron 2019. The use of next generation sequencing for improving food safety: Translation into practice. *Food microbiology*. **79**: 96-115.
 68. de Knecht, Leonardo V., Sara M. Pires, Charlotta Löfström, Gitte Sørensen, Karl Pedersen, Mia Torpdahl, Eva M. Nielsen, and Tine Hald 2016. Application of molecular typing results in source attribution models: the case of multiple locus variable number tandem repeat analysis (MLVA) of *Salmonella* isolates obtained from integrated surveillance in Denmark. *Risk Analysis*. **36(3)**: 571-588.
 69. Maiden Martin C. J., Jane A. Bygraves, Edward Feil, Giovanna Morelli, Joanne E. Russell, Rachel Urwin, Qing Zhang. 1998. Multilocus sequence typing: a portable approach to the identification of clones within populations of pathogenic microorganisms. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. **95(6)**: 3140-3145.
 70. Kotetishvili Mamuka, O. Colin Stine, Arnold Kreger, J. Glenn Morris Jr, and Alexander Sulakvelidze. 2002. Multilocus sequence typing for characterization of clinical and environmental *Salmonella* strains. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*. **40(5)**: 1626-1635.
 71. Aanensen David M., and Brian G. Spratt 2005. The multilocus sequence typing network: mlst. net. *Nucleic acids research*. **33(2)**: W728-W733.
 72. Brehony Carina, Keith A. Jolley, and Martin CJ Maiden 2007. Multilocus sequence typing for global surveillance of meningococcal disease.” *FEMS microbiology reviews*. **31(1)**: 15-26.
 73. David M. D., T. M. A. Weller, P. Lambert, and A. P. Fraise 2006. An outbreak of *Serratia marcescens* on the neonatal unit: a tale of two clones. *Journal of Hospital Infection*. **63(1)**: 27-33.
 74. Franco-Duarte, Ricardo, Lucia Černáková, Snehal Kadam, Karishma S. Kaushik, Bahare Salehi, Antonio Bevilacqua, Maria Rosaria Corbo 2019. Advances in chemical and biological methods to identify microorganisms—from past to present. *Microorganisms*. **7(5)**: 130.
 75. Tewolde Rediat, Timothy Dallman, Ulf Schaefer, Carmen L. Sheppard, Philip Ashton, Bruno Pichon, Matthew Ellington, Craig Swift, Jonathan Green, and Anthony Underwood 2016. MOST: a modified MLST typing tool based on short read sequencing. *PeerJ*. **4**: e2308.

76. Pérez-Losada, Marcos, Miguel Arenas, and Eduardo Castro-Nallar 2018. Microbial sequence typing in the genomic era. *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*. **63**: 346-359.
77. Johnson Douglas I., and Douglas I. Johnson 2018. *Bacterial virulence factors*. Springer International Publishing.
78. Fournier Pierre-Edouard, Gregory Dubourg, and Didier Raoult 2014. Clinical detection and characterization of bacterial pathogens in the genomics era. *Genome medicine*. **6**: 1-15.
79. Karlin Samuel 2001. Detecting anomalous gene clusters and pathogenicity islands in diverse bacterial genomes. *Trends in microbiology*. **9(7)**: 335-343.
80. Gao Ruimin, Hongsheng Huang, Jérémie Hamel, Roger C. Levesque, Lawrence D. Goodridge, and Dele Ogunremi 2022. Application of a high-throughput targeted sequence AmpliSeq procedure to assess the presence and variants of virulence genes in *Salmonella*. *Microorganisms*. **10(2)**: 369.
81. Wu Xingwen, Hao Luo, Chongtao Ge, Feng Xu, Xiangyu Deng, Martin Wiedmann, Robert C. Baker, Abigail E. Stevenson, Guangtao Zhang, and Silin Tang. 2023. Evaluation of multiplex nanopore sequencing for *Salmonella* serotype prediction and antimicrobial resistance gene and virulence gene detection. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. **13**: 1073057.
82. Suez Jotham, Steffen Porwollik, Amir Dagan, Alex Marzel, Yosef Ilan Schorr, Prerak T. Desai, Vered Agmon, Michael McClelland, Galia Rahav, and Ohad Gal-Mor. 2013. Virulence gene profiling and pathogenicity characterization of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* accounted for invasive disease in humans. *PloS one*. **8(3)**: e58449.
83. Tang Ka Wah Kelly, Beverley C. Millar, and John E. Moore 2023. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR). " *British Journal of Biomedical Science*. **80**: 11387.
84. McDermott Patrick F., Gregory H. Tyson, Claudine Kabera, Yuansha Chen, Cong Li, Jason P. Folster, Sherry L. Ayers, Claudia Lam, Heather P. Tate, and Shaohua Zhao 2016. Whole-genome sequencing for detecting antimicrobial resistance in nontyphoidal *Salmonella*. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy*. **60(9)**: 5515-5520.
85. Boolchandani, Manish, Alaric W. D'Souza, and Gautam Dantas 2019. Sequencing-based methods and resources to study antimicrobial resistance. *Nature Reviews Genetics*. **20(6)**: 356-370.
86. Ocejo Medelin, Beatriz Oporto, José Luis Lavín, and Ana Hurtado 2021. Whole genome-based characterisation of antimicrobial resistance and genetic diversity in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* from ruminants. *Scientific Reports*. **11(1)**: 8998.
87. Mahfouz Norhan, Inês Ferreira, Stephan Beisen, Arndt von Haeseler, and Andreas E. Posch 2020. Large-scale assessment of antimicrobial resistance marker databases for genetic phenotype prediction: a systematic review. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. **75(11)**: 3099-3108.
88. Jackson C. R., J. A. Davis, J. G. Frye, J. B. Barrett, and L. M. Hiott 2015. Diversity of Plasmids and Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in Multidrug Resistant *Escherichia coli* Isolated from Healthy Companion Animals. *Zoonoses and Public Health*. **62(6)**: 479-488.
89. Moura Alexandra, Alexis Criscuolo, Hannes Pouseele, Mylène M. Maury, Alexandre Leclercq, Cheryl Tarr, Jonas T. Björkman 2016. Whole genome-based population biology and epidemiological surveillance of *Listeria monocytogenes*. *Nature microbiology*. **2(2)**: 1-10.
90. Besser John M., Heather A. Carleton, Eija Trees, Steven G. Stroika, Kelley Hise, Matthew Wise, and Peter Gerner-Smidt 2019. Interpretation of whole-genome sequencing for enteric disease surveillance and outbreak investigation. *Foodborne pathogens and disease*. **16(7)**: 504-512.
91. Pennone Vincenzo, José Francisco Cobo Díaz, Miguel Prieto Maradona, and Avelino Álvarez Ordóñez 2022. Integration of genomics in surveillance and risk assessment for outbreak investigation." *EFSA Journal* **20**: e200417.
92. Sekse Camilla, Arne Holst-Jensen, Ulrich Dobrindt, Gro S. Johannessen, Weihua Li, Bjørn Spilberg, and Jianxin Shi 2017. High throughput sequencing for detection of foodborne pathogens. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. **8**: 2029.

93. **Akinyemi Kabiru Olusegun, Christopher Oladimeji Fakorede, Jörg Linde, Ulrich Methner, Gamal Wareth, Herbert Tomaso, and Heinrich Neubauer 2023.** Whole genome sequencing of *Salmonella enterica* serovars isolated from humans, animals, and the environment in Lagos, Nigeria. *Bmc Microbiology*. **23(1)**: 164.
94. **Gilmour Matthew W., Morag Graham, Gary Van Domselaar, Shaun Tyler, Heather Kent, Keri M 2010.** Trout-Yakel, Oscar Larios, Vanessa Allen, Barbara Lee, and Celine Nadon. High-throughput genome sequencing of two *Listeria monocytogenes* clinical isolates during a large foodborne outbreak." *BMC genomics*. **11**: 1-15.
95. **Deng Xiangyu, Henk C. den Bakker, and Rene S. Hendriksen 2016.** Genomic epidemiology: whole-genome-sequencing-powered surveillance and outbreak investigation of foodborne bacterial pathogens. *Annual review of food science and technology*. **7(1)**: 353-374.
96. **Plumb Ian D., Allison C. Brown, Erin K. Stokes, Jessica C. Chen, Heather Carleton, Beth Tolar, Preethi Sundararaman 2023.** Increased Multidrug-Resistant *Salmonella enterica* I Serotype 4,[5], 12: i:- Infections Associated with Pork, United States, 2009–2018." *Emerging Infectious Diseases*. **29(2)**: 314.
97. **Harris Simon R., and Chinyere K. Okoro. 2014.** Whole-genome sequencing for rapid and accurate identification of bacterial transmission pathways. *In Methods in microbiology*. 41, pp. 123-152. Academic Press.
98. **World Health Organization 2018.** Whole genome sequencing for foodborne disease surveillance: landscape paper.
99. **Mastrorilli Eleonora, Daniele Pietrucci, Lisa Barco, Serena Ammendola, Sara Petrin, Alessandra Longo, Claudio Mantovani 2018.** A comparative genomic analysis provides novel insights into the ecological success of the monophasic *Salmonella serovar*. 4,[5], 12: i:- *Frontiers in microbiology*. **9**: 715.
100. **Karant Shradha, Jitendra Patel, Adel Shirmohammadi, and Abani K. Pradhan 2023.** Machine learning to predict foodborne salmonellosis outbreaks based on genome characteristics and meteorological trends. *Current Research in Food Science* **6**: 100525.
101. **Van Rie, Annelies 2023.** Computational methods for whole genome sequence guided individualized treatment of drug resistant tuberculosis."
102. **Ransom, Eric M., Robert F. Potter, Gautam Dantas, and Carey-Ann D 2020.** Burnham. "Genomic prediction of antimicrobial resistance: ready or not, here it comes!. *Clinical chemistry* 66, no. 10: 1278-1289.
103. **Johansson Markus H. K., Valeria Bortolaia, Supatth Tansirichaiya, Frank M. Aarestrup, Adam P. Roberts, and Thomas N. Petersen. 2021.** Detection of mobile genetic elements associated with antibiotic resistance in *Salmonella enterica* using a newly developed web tool: Mobile Element Finder. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. **76(1)**: 101-109.
104. **Hendriksen, Rene S., Valeria Bortolaia, Heather Tate, Gregory H. Tyson, Frank M. Aarestrup, and Patrick F. McDermott 2019.** Using genomics to track global antimicrobial resistance. *Frontiers in public health*. **7**: 242.
105. **Zankari Ea, Henrik Hasman, Salvatore Cosentino, Martin Vestergaard, Simon Rasmussen, Ole Lund, Frank M. 2012.** Aarestrup, and Mette Voldby Larsen. "Identification of acquired antimicrobial resistance genes." *Journal of antimicrobial chemotherapy*. **67(11)**: 2640-2644.
